

Climate Change Adaptation Strategies among Yam Farmers in Wukari Local Government area, Taraba State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed yam farmers' adaptation strategies to climate change in Wukari Local Government Area, Taraba State, Nigeria. Primary data were collected from 88 respondents using structured questionnaires and analyzed through descriptive statistics and multiple regression. The respondents were predominantly male (58%), with an average age of 42.25 years. Most were married (64%) and had attained formal education (88%). Household sizes were generally small, with 93% of farmers having 15 or fewer members, and 85% had more than 10 years of farming experience. Despite this, only 15% were members of cooperative societies, while 76% had access to credit. Analysis of adaptation strategies showed that the most adopted methods were use of chemicals (27.56%), cultural practices (22.44%), and mixed farming (21.70%), followed by afforestation (10.36%), crop rotation (9.94%), crop diversification (5.76%), and migration (2.24%). Multiple regression analysis revealed that age ($\beta = 0.041$, $p < 0.01$), education ($\beta = 0.118$, $p < 0.05$), farming experience ($\beta = 0.039$, $p < 0.01$), and cooperative membership ($\beta = 0.135$, $p < 0.01$) significantly and positively influenced the adoption of climate change adaptation strategies. Conversely, household size ($\beta = -0.048$, $p < 0.01$) had a significant negative effect. The model explained 87.9% of the variance in adaptation levels ($R^2 = 0.879$, $F = 457.932$, $p < 0.01$). Key constraints to adaptation were limited access to credit (mean = 2.47), unsupportive government policy (mean = 2.36), and high cost of irrigation (mean = 2.22). The study concludes that although yam farmers are aware of and adopt various strategies to cope with climate change, their efforts are hindered by limited institutional support and financial resources. It is recommended that farmers be encouraged to join cooperatives to enhance access to information, credit, and climate-resilient innovations. Government and NGOs should support yam farmers through climate-smart agriculture policies, subsidized irrigation infrastructure, and targeted funding initiatives.

Keywords: Climate change, Yam farming, Adaptation strategies, socioeconomic factors, Wukari, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Yam (*Dioscorea* spp) is an annual tuber and monocot plant. It belongs to the genus “Dioscorea” and the family “dioscoreacea”. The Food plant comprises of 600 species out of which ten species produce edible tubers and only six are cultivated in Africa (Musa, Onu, Vosanka and Anonguku, 2011). As a root crop, the place of yam in the diet of the people in West Africa and in Nigeria in particular cannot be overemphasized. Akinola, Oke, Adesiyun and Famuyini (2019) reported That yam holds important position as a food and industrial crop in the Nigerian economy. Yam production in Nigeria is entirely dominated by small-scale farmers (Baimey,2006). Yam production in Nigeria is among the most susceptible to the deleterious effects of climate change (Oluwasusi and Tijani, 2013). This is because; the production of this crop like every other crop is affected by factors varying from physical through economic to cultural factors. Climate, one of the physical factors, is the most crucial factor, which determines the nature of the natural vegetation, the characteristics of the soils, the crops that can be grown, and the type of farming that can be practiced in any region (Obiokoro, 2005). Hence, any variation in climatic condition will have significant effects on crop productivity, especially yam yield.

Elijah, Osuafor and Anarah (2018) asserted that climate change is no longer a trivial issue; it is a reality that is seriously affecting the earth already, especially challenging agricultural productivity and food security in both developed and developing economies of the world and thus requires urgent attention. Similarly, Falola and Achem (2017) posited that climate change is gradually attaining a catastrophic dimension given the associated impacts in the various key socio-economic sectors in recent time. One of these sectors is agriculture, specifically the crop sector, which appears to be most susceptible to this phenomenon. Climate affects various aspects of plant growth and development. In fact, it has been earlier predicted that climate change is likely to reduce yields and/or damage crops in the 21st century (IPCC 2001).

Adaptation seems to be the most significant option for the subsistence farmers if they must thrive in the business of farming. According to Zilberman, Zhao and Heirman (2012), adaptation is the response of economic agents and societies to major shocks such as climate change. Adaptation practices are adjustments intended to enhance resilience or reduce vulnerability to observed or expected changes in climate (IPCC, 2001). IPCC (2007) defined adaptation to climate change as an adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities. It also refers to all adjustments in behavior or economic structure that reduce the vulnerability of society to changes in the climate system including its current variability and extreme events as well as longer-term climate change. Adaptation to climate change is imperative to sustain and promote agricultural productivity, and site-specific empirical evidence is needed to facilitate policy making (Roco, *et. al.*, 2017). Obayelu, Adepoju, and Idowu (2014) noted that the goal of adaptation to climate change is neither to prevent its negative impacts nor merely clean up after its adverse effects. Rather, it is a long-term resilience, to create the conditions in which the society is largely able to absorb the impacts, such that any residual impact bey small-scale farmers (Baimey, 2006). Yam production in Nigeria is among the most susceptible to the deleterious effects of climate change (Oluwasusi & Tijani, 2013). Hence, any variation in climatic condition will have significant effects on crop productivity, especially yam yield.

Statement of the Problem

The impact of climate change in agricultural productivity is increasingly becoming alarming to agriculturists in Africa and Nigeria in particular. Crop production which is largely subsistence in Africa is constantly being hindered by the substantial effects of climate change. This has affected food prices, food security, land use as observed by Lobell and Field (2007). Kahil, Connor and Albiac (2015) asserted that the severity of climate change impact Depends on the degree of adaptation at the farm level, farmers' investment decisions and policy choices. However, Farmers are constantly confronted with the challenges of choosing the best adaptation option(s) that will be resilient to the impact of climate change. Moreover, some of the farmers' socio-economic factors may also influence their Decisions and choices in adopting relevant adaptation strategies.

Although, there are influx of literatures on climate change and adaptation strategies among farmers in Africa (Maddison, 2007; Deressa *et al.*, 2008; Agabi, 2012; Ozor, *et al.*, 2012; Bosello, Campagnolo and Eboli, 2013; Umunakwe, Nnadi, Chikaire & Nnadi, 2014; Amusa, Okoye and Enete, 2015; Roco, *et al.*, 2017), stakeholders keep Wondering whether these bulk of literatures have effected any significant positive outcome in crop production (Bosello, *et al.*, 2013). The current escalation in food prices, decrease in crop yields among farmers, increased Poverty among the farming households, and the likes seem to reveal that more studies are needed in this area to Proffer feasible solutions to the rural farmers. Moreover, Enete and Onyekuru (2011) observed that much of climatic Change agricultural research has tended to concentrate on assessing the sensitivity of various attributes of crop Systems (e.g. crop yields, pest, diseases, weeds etc.) – the biophysical aspects of food production, with little or no Regard to the socioeconomic aspects. These partial assessments most often consider climatic change effects in Isolation, providing little insight into the socio-economic factors influencing farmers' decisions and choices of Adaptation strategies and what they are doing to cope with climate change. This could be one of the reasons why the Farmers are still facing critical setback in crop production. This therefore, makes this study worthwhile.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study was to explore yam farmers' adaptation practices towards climate change disaster In Wukari Taraba state, Nigeria. Specifically, the study was meant to:

- i. To describe the socioeconomic characteristics of the yam farmers.
- ii. To describe the adaptation strategies adopted and intensity of adaptation by yam farmers in adjusting to the impacts of climate change on yam production in the study area.
- iii. To analyze the socioeconomic factors influencing yam production activities in the study area.
- iv. To identify the constraints of yam farmers in implementing adaptation strategies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Study Area

The research setting is Wukari Local Government Area Taraba state. Wukari is a local Government in Taraba state, and it is the home of the paramount ruler of the kwararafa kingdom. The local government area is boarded to the north by Ibi local government area, to

the east by Gassol local government area, to the south by Donga local government area and to the west by Ukum local government area of Benue state. The local government is traceable at latitude 7° and 5°N of the equator and between longitude 9° and 47°E of the Greenwich Meridian with a total area of 4,308 Km² (1,663 square mile)

Wukari local government area was created in 1976 and is divided into 15 traditional administrative districts namely Wukari, Aviy, Matar-Fada, Gidan Idi, Tsokundi, Nwoky, Rafin-kada, Chonku, Kente, Chinka, Jibu, Assa, Bantaje, Arufu and Akwana. The local government area has ten political wards, these are Akwana ward, Avyi ward, Bantaje ward, Chonku Ward, Hospital ward, Jibu ward, Kente Ward, Puje ward, Rafinkada ward, and Tsokundi ward respectively.

The town is base of wukari federation, a traditional state. Local government area has a population of 318, 400 persons as projected by the national population commission (NPC, 2016). The local government experiences a tropical climate while the local vegetation is the guinea savannah type. It is marked by dry and raining seasons and then the raining season commences in April and last till October while the dry season last from November till March.

The Harmattan; dry cold and dusty wind is the driest period and occur from the month of December to February with Humidity put at 13%. The wet season start in April and last up October of every year. The rainfall pattern supports rain fed rice production while the dry season with abundant sunshine enhances the sun drying of rice for milling. The area also has high temperature ranging from 27%-32% respectively. The major ethnic groups in the areas are the Jukun, TIV, Ichen, Kuteb, Chamber, Fulani and Hausa. But Hausa English and Jukun Language are widely spoken in the area.

On the Economic sense Wukari local government area has a viable agricultural sector with area known for cultivation of a variety of crops such as Yam, Rice and cassava. Wukari with its Environs are blessed with a fertile arable land suitable for large yam production for both subsistence and commercial scale

Figure 1: Map of Wukari showing the study area

Source: (Okó *et al.*, 2017)

Sources of Data and Method of Data Collection

The data for this study was gathered from primary source of data. The survey was conducted using a well-structured questionnaire. The information collected from the individual respondents includes; ages, gender, household size, educational level, marital status, and other information.

Sampling Techniques

The study employed multi-stage sampling techniques was used to obtained relevant data for this research work. Step 1: five wards [puje, jibu, Tsokundi, Rafin-kada, Bantaje] was selected based on their involvement in yam farming. Step 2: two villages each was randomly selected from the five wards sampled giving a total of ten villages, lastly one hundred and twenty respondents was randomly selected from the ten villages sampled in proportion to their involvement in yam farming in the study area.

Table 3.1 Sampling Technique

S/n	Wards	Villages	Population of residence	Sample size
1	Puje	Hyuku	29	09
		Ando-motor	31	06
2	Jibu	Bye-pyi	22	10
		Kata-iko	21	11
3	Tsokundi	Nwuko	35	19
		Tsokundi	18	18
4	Rafin-kada	Gavyo	30	14
		Rafin-kada	19	14
5	Bantaje	Gindin-dorawa	31	06
		Sabongida	16	10
TOTAL		10	251	120

The sample size was determined by using the formula given by Taro Yamane (1967):

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where;

n = sample size;

N = population of the study;

E = error of margin taking at 5% level

Therefore, a total of 120 yam farmers were selected proportionally for the study. (Table1).

$$n = \frac{251}{1+251(0.5)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{251}{1+251(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{251}{1+0.6275}$$

$$n = \frac{251}{1.6275}$$

$$n = 120.43$$

Analytical Technique

Descriptive statistics was used to analyze objectives 1, 2, and 4. While multiple regression was employed to analyze objective 3.

3.5 Model specification

In order to achieve objectives of the study, the model specification is presented below.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 \dots + \varepsilon_0$$

(KOUTSOYIANNIS 2003)

Where,

Y = level of Adaptation strategies

X₁ = Age of the farmer (years)

X₂ = Sex (male=1, female=0)

X₃ = Marital status

X₄ = Household size (Number of people feeding from the same pot}

X₅ = Level of Education (years of formal schooling)

X₆ = Farming Experience (in years)

X₇ = Membership of Cooperative (membership=1, 0= otherwise)

X₈ = Access to Credit (Naira)

Σ₀ = Error term β

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1: socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents

Variables	Frequency (n=88)	Percentage (%)	Mean
Age			
<30	8	9.09	
31-40	24	27.27	
41-50	33	37.50	
51-60	18	20.46	
>60	5	5.68	
Total		100	42.25
Gender			
Male	51	57.96	
Female	37	42.04	
Total		100	
Marital status			
Married	56	63.64	
Single	23	26.14	
Divorce	6	6.81	
Widowed	3	3.41	
Total		100	
Education level			
Non	11	12.49	
Primary	24	27.27	
Secondary	41	46.59	
Tertiary	12	13.65	

Total		100	
Household size			
<5	16	18.18	
6-10	27	30.68	
11-15	39	44.32	
>15	6	6.82	
Total		100	9
Experience			
<10	13	14.76	
11-20	29	32.96	
21-30	31	35.23	
>30	15	17.05	
Total		100	18
Cooperative Member			
Non member	75	85.23	
Member	13	14.77	
Total		100	
Source credit			
Yes	67	76.14	
No	21	23.86	
Total		100	

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 1 present the relevant socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents in the study area.

The results on the table showed that majority of the respondents (94%) were less than 60 years of age, while only 6% were more than 60 years. The mean age of the respondents was 42.25 years, which indicates that the majority of respondents were in their prime or productive age. This means that younger individuals have energy to tackle climatic change effect than their older counterparts. The result revealed that the majority (58%) of the respondents were male while 42% were female. This indicates that they were more male dominating handling climatic change effect in the area. This could be as a result of their relative stronger gender compared to their counterparts, this will make them response to climatic change faster and swifter.

The table also show that most (64%) of the respondents were married in way or other, while 36% were single. It shows that they have the necessary experience of climatic change on their farming activities which will make them to device means of handling the effect of the climatic change. Educational level has been seen as a factor influencing the personality of an individual. The finding revealed that majority (88%) of yam farmers in the area of study had one form of formal education or the other as against only 12% that claimed not to have any form of formal education. This means that majority of the respondents had opportunity of managing and handling climatic change issues through the knowledge they acquired in their respective formal education. The table showed that most (93%) of the respondents had about 15 or less members in their households, while only 7% of the respondents had more than 15 members in their household. This indicated that most of the farmers has less members in their households. This depicts that most respondent will be able to manage climatic change effect on their farms having fewer household members where they can easily direct some of their savings.

Farming experience refers to the number of year's farmer spent in farming enterprise. It may also affect the farmer's means of handling the effect of climatic change. Results on the farming experience revealed that majority (85%) of the yam farmers had farming experience of more than 10 years, while 15% had farming experience of 10 years or less. The result revealed that the respondents had a reasonable of experience. Their cumulative experience will aid them to manage and handle issues of climatic change on their farming activities. Cooperative societies provide assistance to their members in terms of credit to enhance profitability, information on new technologies and serve as medium of communication between members and extension agents which will be of help in handling issues of climatic change among farmers. Most (85%) of the yam farmers do not belong to any farmer's association, while 15% yam farmers belonged to one farmer's association or the other. This means, most respondents were deficient of the benefits of cooperatives in confronting climatic change menace. The table also indicated sourcing credits in the study area which was classified into purchased, inherited and rented. The result shows that majority (76%) of the respondents had access to credit in the study area, while only 14% of the respondents do not have access to credit. This implied that most respondents have access to credit in one way or the other, this will be of help to the farmers in controlling or curing damages caused by climatic change menace.

Table 2: Classification of Respondents Based on their Adaptation on Climatic Change

Adaptation Strategy	*Frequency (n=88)	Percentage (%)	Ranking
Afforestation	32	10.36	4
Migration	7	2.24	7
Crop Diversification	18	5.76	6
Cultural Practices	70	22.44	2
Use of Chemicals	86	27.56	1
Crop Rotation	31	9.94	5
Mixed Farming	68	21.70	3
Total	312	100	

Source: Field survey, 2025

Most of the respondents identified more than one means of adaptation of climatic change on their yam farming activities. Table 2 revealed that the majority (27.56%) of the respondents' uses chemicals on their yam farming as means of managing climatic change on their yam output. Engaging in cultural practices on yam farms like early planting, mulching, staking etc. was second with 22.44% showing that it will reduce advance effect of climatic change on yam farmers output in the study area.

Mixed farming was third with 21.70% revealing that yam farmers involving in diverse farming activities of both crop and animals will be of help to minimize the consequences of climatic on their livelihood. The fourth was afforestation with 10.36% indicating that plating trees will prevent and control the sudden encroachment of desertification, drought and other factors that threatens climatic change in the study area. The fifth was crop rotation with 9.94% depicting that continuous cropping a crop on particular land increase the effect of climatic change on farm, but crop rotation will sustain the quality of particular land over time.

Table 3: Socioeconomic factors affecting adoption of climatic change

Items	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
Constant	1.347	0.257		5.241***
Age	0.041	0.006	0.395	6.833***
Gender	0.071	0.046	0.035	1.5434
Marital Status	0.019	0.015	0.21	1.2666
Household Size	-0.048	0.010	-0.177	-4.996***
Education	0.118	0.047	0.095	2.5106**
Experience	0.039	0.008	0.201	4.875***
Cooperative	0.135	0.029	0.154	4.655***
Income	0.023	0.041	0.011	0.560
F-Value				457.932***
R-Square (R ²)				0.879 (87.9%)

Source: field survey 2025

***Significant at 1% level and ** Significant at 5% level

Table 3 presents the results of a regression analysis examining the socioeconomic factors affecting adoptability of climatic change among yam farmers in Wukari. Overall, the regression model has a high F-value of 457.932 indicating that the model is statistically significant, meaning the model is best fit for the problem at hand. The R-squared value of 0.879 indicates that 87.9% of the variation in adoptability climatic change among yam farmers can be explained by the independent variables included in the model. Age, household size, education, experience and cooperative were significant factors affecting adoptability of climatic change among yam farmers in Wukari.

Age of the respondents was positive and significant at one percent level with coefficient of 0.041. This indicates that for each additional year of a respondent will increase means of adoptability to climatic change by 0.041 units. This opined that respondents that older respondents were forced adopt climatic change effect as compared to younger ones. This could be because the older one become, the more responsible they become and look for means of survival. Household size of the respondents was negative and significant at one percent level with coefficient of 0.048. This depicts that an additional person in household in respondent household will decrease ability of respondent to adopt climatic change effect by 0.041. This unveiled that respondents with larger household size find it difficult to adjust to climatic change than those with fewer household size. This may be because of the high cost of handling climatic change which could threaten respondent little income to carter for the family.

Education level of the respondents was positive and significant at five level with coefficient of 0.118. This opined that and additional year in formal education by respondent will increase chances of increasing another means of adoption of climatic change by 0.118. This indicates that respondents with more years in formal education better placed to sustain climatic change effect compared to those that have not been to school. This supports the need for education in understating phenomena of climatic change and its consequences on yam farming and also having technical know-how to handle it. Experience of yam farming was positive and significant one percent level with coefficient of 0.039. This shows that and additional year of experience by yam farmer will give an opening of having additional means of handling

climatic change by 0.039. This depicts that respondents with more experience in yam farming were have advantage of understanding the effect of climatic change as compared to those with fewer years of experience.

Cooperative membership was positive and significant at one percent level with coefficient of 0.135. This implies that yam farmers that were members of cooperative in one way or the other were more embraced with climatic change issues than those that were not members. This is probably because those that were cooperative members were having opportunity to interact with other member where they share experience on such issues and also can access information on climatic change from government agencies and other related sources of information.

Table 4: Constraints associated with Climatic Change Adoption Strategy n=88

Constraints	Mean Scale	Ranking
Access to credit	2.47	1
Government policy	2.36	2
Difficulty of irrigation practice	2.22	3
Insufficient information	1.55	4
Access to Technology	1.18	5

Source: field survey, 2025

The result on Table 4 showed the constraints associated with strategies of adopting climatic change in the study area, Likert scale was used. Accessing credit was first with the mean of 2.47 revealing that managing the effect of climatic was capital intensive and yam farmers will need credit facilities to achieve it. Second was government policy with mean of 2.36 suggesting that government should have sustainable policies on climatic such as afforestation programs, proper waste management, and environmental protection and support it with resources to all stake holders for positive result.

Third was expensive and high cost of irrigation facilities with the mean of 2.22 implying that, climatic change has advance effect on plants particularly yam as a result of inability of yam farmer compliment water supply on their farms when there was drought even in the raining season, not to talk more of cultivating in dry season.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, most yam farmers involving in adaption of climatic change practices were young, married male farmers that were educated, members of cooperative, with low income and small household size. Their major practices were use of chemicals, cultural practices, mixed farming, afforestation and crop rotation. The major socioeconomic factors affecting them were age, household size, education, experience and cooperative. While their major constraints were accessing credit, government policy and expensive and high cost of irrigation facilities. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that, Yam farmers are advised to join cooperative societies to enable them have more insights on adaption of practices of handling climatic change. Yam farmers are encouraged to engage into practices of handling climatic change in their farming activities to maximize their output. Government and other non-governmental agencies are to support famers with funds to enhance their productivity through handling climatic change menace.

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